

Business Psychology

Psychology

Introduction

- Little is known about mental health in childhood, although the various studies in stages of development has shown some useful information. This is due in part to the characteristics this phase of the life cycle, which is marked by different changes in several areas and very quickly (Moffitt et.al, 2011). It is also due to the fact that most of the behavior expected at this stage (hyperactivity, negativity, aggression, disobedience among others) are the same featuring disorders psychopathology in later stages of development (Rothon et.al, 2011).
- Such as disturbance Behavior Disorder Bad (TCP) which embraces the Attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD), oppositional Defiant (TND) and dissocial Conduct (CT) (Diamond et.al, 2011). There is overwhelming evidence that much psychopathological disorders detected in adolescents and adulthood, such as depression, anxiety, and abuse of substances, including others. (Moffitt et.al, 2011).

Statement of Purpose

- The panorama clinical and social relevance of realization of a preventive nature study that demonstrate behaviors presented by schooling, detecting early on possible behavioral disorders (ADHD characteristics and TN TC) that may affect the psycho-social development of these children.

The Rationale for Conducting the Study

- Studies has shown that adolescent and adult psycho- pathologic disorders have its alert signs presents since the infancy and represents the high cost to the mental health and juvenile justice on wild world scale. This study aim is to describe children behavior in the public basic school. Equally, evaluate if these conducts represents risk to the development of disruptive disorders is being associated to academic failure.(Moffitt et.al, 2011).

Hypothesis

- Ho: Psychological disorders do have an adverse affect on the mental health of adolescents and children.
- H1: It denotes the rejection of proposed hypothesis.

Research Question

- Is there need for psychological counseling for children's?
- What are the implications of mental disorders on adolescents and children?

Method

- The design used is cross-sectional with sampled simple gem and is divided into two distinct stages, screen- gem and evaluation (Rothon et.al, 2011).
- Step I: The method perform a screening of population of students from elementary school and detect children presenting unhealthy behavior. The instruments used to obtain the necessary information are the CBCL scales 6-18 and 6-18 TRF (Rothon et.al, 2011).

- Step II: Clinical interview will be held for parents of children who scored in the clinical level the scales of CBCL at the screening stage. Sample In the first stage of the study estimated the participation approximately 400 children enrolled in classes from 1st to 4th year of elementary school of study public schools, state and locals (Diamond et.al, 2011).

Exclusion Criteria

- Children with significant mental deficiencies widespread around the development and those schooling res that parents do not agree to participate.

Instruments Used

- The psychopathological research in childhood also presented methodological deficiencies. The studies performed of view using different methodologies and consequently informing different prevalence's, the vary between 1% and 50%(Rotheron et.al, 2011).However, when only considers the studies using DSM as diagnostic criteria, the prevalence decreases situation to be between 1.5% and 20%.For this it is likely to use screening scales based on DSM-IV, which is a diagnostic criterion universally(Moffitt et.al, 2011).

Procedure

- The first step was to obtain the agreement of the secretaries municipal and state education department for the study and submitting the project to the committee research ethics (Suldo et.al, 2011).. Holding meeting with the parents of children enrolled in classes from 1st to 4th grade level I.

- The purpose of the meeting is to present to parents the basis of the study, invite them to participate and to answer the questionnaires. To those parents who agree to cooperate will be harvested signing the Informed Consent and Clarified (IC). The teachers of these children that parents accept to participate will receive support staff (psychologists in training) to answer the questionnaire on the child's behavior at the school. (Moffitt et.al, 2011).

References

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- Suldo, S., Thalji, A., & Ferron, J. (2011). Longitudinal academic outcomes predicted by early adolescents' subjective well-being, psychopathology, and mental health status yielded from a dual factor model. *The Journal of Positive Psychology*, 6(1), 17-30.